

What is the investment?

Initial investment depends on scale and integration with existing infrastructure (e.g. digesters or nitrification-denitrification units).

CAPEX	€200,000 – €500,000 (for mid-to large-scale stripper-scrubber systems)
Operational Cost (OPEX)	€9 – €14 per ton of thin fraction treated
Return on Investment (ROI)	Favorable only at larger processing scales or when integrated with digesters or nitrification-denitrification units

Further details

Total budget: € 75.000,00

Total financed: € 75.000,00

Main funding source: Rural development 2014-2020 for Operational Groups

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RENURE

Economic viability of stripping and scrubbing process for RENURE production

Why implement this innovation on your farm?

In regions with intensive livestock farming, nutrient surpluses—especially nitrogen—can lead to costly environmental compliance and extra manure treatment or transport requirements. The **stripping-scrubbing** system allows farms to **recover ammonium nitrogen** from the liquid fraction of slurry or digestate as **ammonium sulfate or ammonium nitrate**, reducing the nitrogen load in manure and producing a **marketable, RENURE-compliant fertiliser**.

This solution helps:

- Reduce manure disposal costs in high manure pressure zones such as Flanders;
- Produce fertilisers from waste with **lower carbon footprint** compared to synthetic nitrogen fertilisers from Haber-Bosch process;
- Improve nutrient circularity and farm sustainability;
- Decrease reliance on the import of fertiliser or high energy cost for fertiliser production;
- Ensure compliance with **Nitrate Directive thresholds**;

Example of Stripping and scrubbing unit (picture from NUTRIMAN.net provided by Circular Values BV)

Key parameters impacting investment

- Manure type (pig > cattle in NH₄⁺ content)
- Scale (>20,000 tons/year needed for viability)
- Availability of residual heat (e.g., from digesters)
- Existing N removal technologies (for synergy)

Main benefits

- **High nitrogen recovery:**
1.0–2.0 kg N/ton
- **Climate impact reduction:**
Lower GHG emissions than Haber-Bosch fertilizers
- **Cost efficiency:** Economies of scale lower per-ton costs
- **Fertilizer production:**
Marketable ammonium salts (7–15% N)
- **Manure pressure relief:**
Especially valuable in nitrate vulnerable zones
- **Circular nutrient economy:**
Promotes sustainable farming

When do I start saving money?

Savings depend on:

- Scale (minimum threshold: 20,000 tons/year)
- Nitrogen pressure in your region (shadow prices up to €2/kg N in Flanders)
- Presence of a digester or nitrification-denitrification system (significant cost savings in combined setups)

Example (Flemish pig farm with nitrification-denitrification):

- At 24,810 tons/year: **0.2 €/ton saved, 1.05 kg N recovered/ton**
- At 45,370 tons/year: **0.7 €/ton saved, up to 47.6 tons N recovered annually**

Digesters with heat recovery offer even better performance:

- At 48,298 tons/year: **€1.78/ton saved, 1.5–2.0 kg N recovered/ton**

When will I recover my investment?

Economically viable only when:

- Processing scale is medium to large (> 20,000 tons manure to be treated annually)
- A digester or biological N removal unit is already present
- Regional manure pressure is high

Payback period: Estimated at 6–10 years depending on setup and fertilizer market conditions

Ammonium salts produced meet RENURE standards and may substitute synthetic fertilizers under future regulations—**increasing their market value.**

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